

**THEORETICAL EXPLORATION OF ANTI-INFLAMMATORY
PEPTIDES FROM THE LEAVES OF *Spinacea oleracea* L.**

BY

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**A PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF
BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES, COLLEGE OF NATURAL AND APPLIED
SCIENCES, McPHERSON UNIVERSITY, SERIKI SOTAYO, OGUN
STATE, NIGERIA**

**IN PARTIAL FUFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT FOR THE
AWARD OF BACHELOR OF SCIENCES (B.Sc.) DEGREE IN
BIOCHEMISTRY OF THE McPHERSON UNIVERSITY, SERIKI
SOTAYO, OGUN STATE, NIGERIA**

JULY, 2022

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this project was carried out by SOREMEKUN Oyindamola Esther in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of Bachelor of Sciences (B.Sc.) degree in Biochemistry, College of Natural and Applied Sciences, McPherson University, Seriki Sotayo, Ogun State, Nigeria.

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DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to God for the strength and grace he granted upon me from my start to the conclusion of my University days. I also dedicate this project to my parents, Mr. and Mrs Soremekun for their never-ending prayers and support they showed me through this journey.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

My sincere gratitude goes to God Almighty for His grace and protection during the period of this research. This research work would not have been possible without the support of my supervisor, Dr. Babatunde Oso. I appreciate his guidance, patience, criticism and encouragement which helped me in completing this project. May God bless you abundantly.

I also appreciate my Head of Department, Biological Sciences, Dr. Michael Osho for his support and immense knowledge in research. I also acknowledge my lecturers, Dr. Olubukola Agboola, Mr. Ige Olaoye and Dr. Sunday Omieke for their support, guidance and insightful comments.

My genuine appreciation goes to my treasured parents, Dr. & Mrs. O.O. Soremekun. They have instilled in me the spiritual, ethical and educational value which reflects in who I am today. I thank them for their constant prayers, love, and sacrifices. To my brothers, Oluwatosin and Similoluwa, I really appreciate your love, reassurance and ideas.

I am thankful to God for my incredible project partner, Blessing Akofiranmi for her care and for making this project very precious.

I sincerely thank my colleagues and friends, Omodehinde Ferdinard, Akinkunmi Oluwatominsin, Timothy Abigail, Soyemi Melody, Awogbami Jesulayomi, Abisola Crispin, Adelakun Dara Aderinto Hannah, Adeyemo Tijesunimi and Olajunmoke Elisha for making my pursuit for knowledge in McPherson University notable. I appreciate you all.

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ABSTRACT

The treatment of inflammatory disorders is usually linked to vague drugs that can cause undesirable side effects. Peptides have shown anti-inflammatory properties by inhibiting, reducing the expression and activity of mediators of inflammation such as (NF- κ b, MAPK and JAK-STAT). Leafy greens (Spinach, *Spinacea oleracea* L.) are filled with vitamins which is a natural antioxidant which reduces inflammation in the body. This study investigated the anti-inflammatory action of peptides from Spinach (*Spinacea oleracea*), towards selected proteins through computational studies. The peptides were retrieved from the antimicrobial peptide database and their respective physicochemical properties were predicted using ProtParam Tool. The binding mode and the binding free energies were computed through HawkDock servers while the structural flexibility and stability of the ACE2-peptide complexes were evaluated via the CABS-flex 2.0 server. The peptides showed an optimum binding affinity with the respective targets; SOP4 showed the highest binding free energy compared to other peptides. Besides, molecular dynamic simulations showed that all plant-based peptides could influence the flexibility and anti-inflammatory properties of the selected proteins with the RMSF plots. The study revealed that plant-based peptides could be explored for their anti-inflammatory properties in the treatment of inflammatory disorders.

CHAPTER ONE

Introduction

1.1 Background of the study

Inflammation is an immune response leading to the recruitment and activation of protective molecules, known as pro-inflammatory mediators like tumour necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), interleukin (IL)-1, IL-6, IL-8, and interferon- γ (INF- γ), to the site of infection or tissue damage. These mediators can amplify the inflammatory response by interacting with various cellular and subcellular components in different cell types. Moreover, the pathways involving nuclear factor kappa-light enhancer of activated B cells (NF- κ B), Mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPK) and Janus kinase-signal transducer and activator of transcription (JAK-STAT) have also been shown to play crucial roles in the mediation of inflammatory response. These regulatory proteins co-ordinately regulate cell proliferation etc.

However, excessive and uncontrolled production of such mediators from the immune cells leads to tissue damage and loss of immune function. The inflammatory response can be acute (momentary effects followed by healing) like local tissue damage or chronic (continuing effects, not resolved). It has been shown that chronic-inflammatory responses are often associated with disease pathogenesis like Type-2 diabetes, inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), arthritis, atherosclerosis, and other cardiovascular diseases (Ferrero *et al.*,2007). According to epidemiological and clinical studies, 15–20% of malignancies worldwide are developed due to chronic inflammation, and it has become a public threat in both developed and developing countries leading to morbidity and mortality (Kuper *et al.*, 2000). The inflammatory responses

could be treated with anti-inflammatory drugs. However, most of the present pharmacological interventions are inadequate to control chronic inflammatory responses and are also associated with adverse side effects due to the prolonged consumption (Roubille *et al.*, 2013). Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) include cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) selective inhibitors (also known as coxibs), non-selective NSAIDs (nsNSAIDs), aspirin, and glucocorticoids. Although, both coxibs and the traditional nsNSAIDs are equally effective against inflammation, cardiovascular risks are shared by all the NSAIDs, except aspirin. For instance, a latest meta-analysis reported that cerebrovascular and cardiovascular risks are associated with all NSAIDs, at different levels, when compared with placebo. Highest risk of myocardial infraction was associated with rofecoxib, followed by lumiracoxib (Trelle *et al.*, 2011). Hence, it is always judicious to assess the patient's cardiovascular risk before these drugs can be prescribed (Antman *et al.*, 2007). Although the chronic inflammatory diseases have different aetiologies, inflammatory pathways leading to the pathological abnormalities are shared, and thus these inflammatory pathways can be used as potential targets for the development of curative and preventive treatment for the diseases related to chronic inflammatory responses (Vendramini *et al.*, 2012; Majumder *et al.*, 2016). Thus, there is an urgent need for developing alternative and safer therapeutic options from the natural products or foods.

Plant-based peptides have been elected as lead compounds towards several targets for their high specificity and innovative strategies (La Manna *et al.*, 2017). Peptides have shown anti-inflammatory properties by inhibiting, reducing the expression and activity of mediators of inflammation (Anderson *et al.*, 2008). Leafy vegetables contain vital bioactive compounds with anti-inflammatory properties. Examples of such plants include blueberries (*Vaccinium sect.cyanococcus*), spinach (*Spinacea oleracea*), or Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) and spirulina

(*Arthrospira platensis*). Spinach supplementation had been shown to reduce ischemic brain damage, an inflammatory disorder (Wang *et al.*, 2005).

Spinach (*Spinacea oleracea* L.) is a flowering plant in the Amaranthaceae family. Though spinach is most commonly used as a food, it also has medicinal properties. Natural antioxidant (NAO), a water-soluble extract obtained from spinach leaves, has been shown to have anti-inflammatory (Lomnitski *et al.*, 2000), anti-proliferative and anti-oxidative properties in biological systems (Bergman *et al.*, 2001). Despite available literatures on the hypothetical roles of spinach in the mediation of inflammatory response, the mode of action of some of the anti-inflammatory component vis-à-vis the MAPK pathway is yet to be investigated. Thus, this study aimed at investigating the anti-inflammatory effect of peptides of *Spinacea oleracea* on Mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPK) enzymes. The enzymes include EGFR (Epidermal growth factor), MEK1 (threonine and tyrosine recognition kinase), erbB2 (a tumour suppressor) (Nature, 1992). These enzymes will be taken into consideration in this study.

1.2 Justification of study

Inflammation is an immune response leading to the recruitment and activation of protective molecules, known as pro-inflammatory mediators. However, excessive and uncontrolled production of such mediators from the immune cells leads to tissue damage and loss of immune function. Bioactive proteins and peptides from different sources have various bioactivity attributes like anti-viral, antibacterial, antifungal, antiparasitic, antihypertensive, antispasmodic, and anticancer. *Spinacea oleracea* has been discovered to have a high content of bioactive peptides that have immense therapeutic applications. Despite available literatures on the

hypothetical roles of spinach in the mediation of inflammatory response, the mode of action of some of the anti-inflammatory component vis-à-vis the MAPK pathway is yet to be investigated. Thus, this study aimed at investigating the anti-inflammatory effect of peptides of *Spinacea oleracea* on Mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPK) enzymes.

1.3 General Objective

The overall objective of this study was to explore the theoretical study on plant-based anti-inflammatory peptides from the leaves of *Spinacea oleracea* using computational methods.

1.4 Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of the study include:

- screening of databases for the selection of bioactive peptides of *Spinacea oleracea*;
- retrieval and modelling of the selected peptides;
- physicochemical characterization of the selected peptides;
- prediction of the interactions of the selected peptides with EGFR, and MEK1 through molecular docking; and
- analysis of the induced structural changes in the selected enzymes.

CHAPTER TWO

Literature review

2.1 Inflammation as a disease

Inflammation is part of the body's defence mechanism and plays a role in the healing process. When the body detects an intruder, it launches a biological response to try to remove it. The attacker could be a foreign body, such as a thorn, an irritant, or a pathogen. Pathogens include bacteria, viruses, and other organisms, which cause infections. Sometimes, the body mistakenly perceives its own cells or tissues as harmful. This reaction can lead to autoimmune diseases, such as type 1 diabetes. Experts believe inflammation may contribute to a wide range of chronic diseases. Examples of these are metabolic syndrome, which includes type 2 diabetes, heart disease, and obesity. People with these conditions often have higher levels of inflammatory markers in their bodies.

There are two main types of inflammation: acute inflammation and chronic inflammation.

Acute inflammation may be a short-term injury or illness. The signs of acute inflammation are; rubor (redness); This happens because of an increase in the blood supply to the capillaries in the area, calor (increased heat) Increased blood flow may leave the affected area warm to the touch.), tumor (swelling) A condition called oedema can develop if fluid builds up, dolor (pain) This may occur continuously or only when a person touches the affected area, and functio laesa (loss of function) There may be difficulty moving a joint, breathing, sensing smell, and so on. Sometimes inflammation is "silent," without symptoms. A person may also feel tired, generally

unwell, and have a fever. Symptoms of acute inflammation last a few days. Subacute inflammation lasts 2–6 weeks.

Chronic inflammation can develop if a person has:

- Sensitivity:** Inflammation happens when the body senses something that should not be there. Hypersensitivity to an external trigger can result in an allergy.
- Sometimes, long-term, low-level exposure to an irritant, such as an industrial chemical, can result in chronic inflammation, also autoimmune disorders where the immune system mistakenly attacks normal healthy tissue, as in psoriasis, auto inflammatory diseases where a genetic factor affects the way the immune system works, as in Behçet's disease.
- Persistent acute inflammation:** In some cases, a person may not fully recover from acute inflammation. Sometimes, this can lead to chronic inflammation. Factors that may increase the risk of chronic inflammation include: older age, obesity, a diet that is rich in unhealthy fats and added sugar, smoking, low sex hormones, stress, sleep problems. Long-term diseases that doctors associate with inflammation include: asthma, chronic peptic ulcer, tuberculosis, rheumatoid arthritis, periodontitis, ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease sinusitis active hepatitis.

Inflammation plays a vital role in healing, but chronic inflammation may increase the risk of various diseases, including some cancers, rheumatoid arthritis, atherosclerosis, periodontitis, and hay fever.

Chronic inflammation can continue for months or years. It either has or may have links to various diseases, such as; diabetes, cardiovascular disease (CVD), arthritis and other joint diseases, allergies, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), psoriasis, rheumatoid arthritis. The symptoms will depend on the disease, but they may include pain and fatigue. When inflammation is present in the body, there will be higher levels of pro-inflammatory biomarkers. An example of such biomarkers is C-reactive protein (CRP).

2.2 Diseases associated with dysfunctional inflammatory response

The inflammatory response is the coordinate activation of signalling pathways that regulate inflammatory mediator levels in resident tissue cells and inflammatory cells recruited from the blood (Lawrence *et al.*, 2009). Inflammation is a common pathogenesis of many chronic diseases, including cardiovascular and bowel diseases, diabetes, arthritis, and cancer (Libby *et al.*, 2007). Although inflammatory response processes depend on the precise nature of the initial stimulus and its location in the body, they all share a common mechanism, which can be summarized as follows:

- 1) Cell surface pattern receptors recognize detrimental stimuli
- 2) Inflammatory pathways are activated
- 3) Inflammatory markers are released
- 4) Inflammatory cells are recruited.

Aetiology of Inflammation

Type of Agents include biological, Chemical\ Physical and Immune reactions

Biological agents; examples are infectious agents e.g viruses, bacteria etc, necrotic tissue e.g dead heart muscle in myocardial infection. Different types of micro-organisms incite different types of inflammatory responses e.g bacteria – acute inflammation; viruses- chronic inflammation. Chemical\ Physical; examples are poisons, Toxins; trauma causing tissue injury or foreign body (e.g splinter). Immune reactions; examples are Auto-immune diseases: immune response to self-antigens, immune response to foreign tissues like allergens etc. It is seen more in chronic inflammation.

2.2 Causes of inflammation

Inflammation happens when a physical factor triggers an immune reaction. Inflammation does not necessarily mean that there is an infection, but an infection can cause inflammation. Acute inflammation can result from: exposure to a substance, such as a bee sting or dust, an injury, an infection. When the body detects damage or pathogens, the immune system triggers a number of reactions:

Tissues accumulate plasma proteins, leading to a build-up of fluid that results in swelling.

The body releases neutrophils, a type of white blood cell, or leukocyte, which move toward the affected area. Leukocytes contain molecules that can help fight pathogens.

Small blood vessels enlarge to enable leukocytes and plasma proteins to reach the injury site more easily. Signs of acute inflammation can appear within hours or days, depending on the cause. In some cases, they can rapidly become severe. How they develop and how long they last will depend on the cause, which part of the body they affect, and individual factors.

2.3 Common treatments

Treatment of inflammation will depend on the cause and severity. Often, there is no need for treatment. Sometimes, however, not treating inflammation can result in life threatening symptoms. During an allergic reaction, for example, inflammation can cause severe swelling that may close the airways, making it impossible to breathe. It is essential to have treatment if this reaction occurs. Without treatment, some infections can enter the blood, resulting in sepsis. This is another life threatening condition that needs urgent medical treatment.

Acute inflammation: A doctor may prescribe treatment to remove the cause of inflammation, manage symptoms, or both. For a bacterial or fungal infection, for example, they may prescribe

antibiotics or antifungal treatment. Here are some treatments specifically for treating inflammation:

2.3.1 Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAID's)

Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) will not remove the cause of inflammation, but they can help relieve pain, swelling, fever, and other symptoms. They do this by countering an enzyme that contributes to inflammation. Examples of NSAIDs include naproxen, ibuprofen, and aspirin. These are available to purchase online or over the counter. People should check first with a doctor or pharmacist to ensure they make the right choice.

2.3.2 Corticosteroids

Corticosteroids, such as cortisol, are a type of steroid hormone. They affect various mechanisms involved in inflammation. Corticosteroids can help manage a range of conditions, including: arthritis, temporal arteritis, dermatitis, inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) etc. They are available as pills, injections, in an inhaler, or as creams or ointments. Long-term use of corticosteroids can be harmful. A doctor can advise on their risks and benefits.

2.3.3 Herbs for the treatment of inflammation

Various herbal supplements may help manage inflammation. *Harpagophytum procumbens*: Also known as devil's claw, wood spider, or grapple plant, this herb comes from South Africa and is related to sesame plants. Some older research from 2011 has shown it may have anti-inflammatory properties. Various brands are available to purchase online, Hyssop which people can mix with other herbs, such as licorice, for the treatment of some lung conditions, including airway inflammation. However, the hyssop essential oil has led to life threatening convulsions in laboratory animals, so caution is necessary, Ginger has also been used by people to treat

dyspepsia, constipation, colic, and other gastrointestinal problems, as well as rheumatoid arthritis pain. Ginger is available fresh in groceries or online in supplement form, Turmeric (Curcumin), the main ingredient in turmeric, may have benefits for arthritis, Alzheimer's disease, and some other inflammatory conditions. Supplements with turmeric and curcumin are available online, Cannabis: A cannabinoid called cannabichromene may have anti-inflammatory properties. People should check first if cannabis-related products are legal where they live.

2.4 Cellular setup and molecular mediators of inflammation

At the cellular level, we characterize how these pathways are regulated depending on cellular identity. At the molecular level, we identify and characterize new pathways involved in triggering inflammatory pathologies.

The inflammatory environment with fluid leaking out the blood vessels creates the conditions for white cell adhesion to the blood vessel wall since the blood flow starts to slowdown. This is the initial step of a serial process moving out the white cells from the vessel lumen to the interstitium of the damaged tissue. Two major aspects related to the body's reaction to inflammation are the speed and the amount of white cells taken to the target tissue. Phagocytes are the predominant form of leukocytes designated to clean up the site of injury, eating bacteria and strange elements, removing the cellular remains produced during the injury progress.

Neutrophils are a class of white cells involved in acute inflammation. This particular type of phagocyte holds granules of enzymes capable of destroying toxic substances, such as reactive oxygen species, proteins, and cells, making these cells the major components in the injury processing. For local and weak damages, the amount of circulating neutrophils is enough for inflammatory response. However, for wide damages, sources of neutrophils from the bone

marrow are constantly requested for acting on the injured site as the early agents. Even if in its immature form, neutrophils can reach the local spot quickly after the inflammatory process starts (Nathan *et al.*, 2010).

Monocytes are the second group of blood cells requested for acting on the inflamed area, usually several hours after the beginning of this process. These white blood cells when matured are called macrophages, and they are responsible for the ultimate step of engulfing and disposing the invasive cells and foreign elements. Macrophages are also the predominant agents in the chronic inflammation healing.

2.4.1 Pathways relating to inflammation and their activation

Inflammatory pathways impact the pathogenesis of a number of chronic diseases, and involve common inflammatory mediators and regulatory pathways. Inflammatory stimuli activate intracellular signalling pathways that then activate production of inflammatory mediators. Primary inflammatory stimuli, including microbial products and cytokines such as interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), mediate inflammation through interaction with the TLRs, IL-1 receptor (IL-1R), IL-6 receptor (IL-6R), and the TNF receptor (TNFR)(Kaminska *et al.*, 2005). These mediators trigger the inflammatory responses via activation of various signalling pathways. The inflammatory mediators could be exogenous (originating outside the body) or endogenous. The endogenous mediators could be further classified on the basis of their origin: plasma (complement, kinin, and coagulation are the prime mediator generating systems), cell-derived (such as platelet activating factors, IL-1, and leukotrienes), and originating within the cells (neutrophils containing cationic proteins and histamine in mast cells). The nuclear factor-kappa light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells (NF-

JB) pathway and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathway are the two most crucial primary signalling pathways responsible for maintaining the defence system against harmful stimuli. However, when these signals become excessive and uncontrolled, it leads to chronic inflammation (Majumder *et al.*, 2016). The NF- κ B pathway is involved in various functions such as production of cytokines (IL-1b, IL-6, IL-8, and TNF-a), induction of inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), and regulation of cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) expression. In vascular endothelial cells, activation of NF- κ B up-regulates the expression of adhesion molecules including vascular cell adhesion molecule-1 (VCAM-1), intercellular adhesion molecule-1 (ICAM-1), and E-selectin. NF- κ B is thought to be the fundamental regulator of gene expression during inflammation, which is a transcription factor present in the cytoplasm of different cell-types (Tak *et al.*, 2001).

NF- κ B, MAPK, and JAK-STAT, also play major roles in inflammation, and dysregulation of one or more of these pathways may lead to inflammation-associated disease.

2.4.1.1 NF- κ B

The NF- κ B is an important transcription factor that plays significant roles in inflammatory, immune response, survival, and apoptosis processes (Girard *et al.*, 2009). The NF- κ B family includes five related transcription factors: P50, p52, RelA (p65), Rel B, and c-Rel (Moynagh *et al.*, 2005). NF- κ B activity is induced by a range of stimuli, including pathogen-derived substances, intercellular inflammatory cytokines, and many enzymes (Pasparakis *et al.*, 2006). Under physiological conditions, I κ B proteins present in the cytoplasm inhibit NF- κ B (Kadhim *et al.*, 2001). PRRs use similar signal transduction mechanisms to activate I κ B kinase (IKK), which is composed of two kinase subunits, IKK α and IKK β , and a regulatory subunit, such as IKK γ . IKK regulates NF- κ B pathway activation through I κ B phosphorylation (Lawrence *et al.*, 2009).

I κ B phosphorylation results in its degradation by the proteasome and the subsequent release of NF- κ B for nuclear translocation and gene transcription activation (Hayden *et al.*, 2012). This pathway regulates pro-inflammatory cytokine production and inflammatory cell recruitment, which contribute to the inflammatory response. This pathway is triggered by TLRs and inflammatory cytokines, such as TNF and IL-1, leading to activation of RelA/p50 complexes that regulate expression of inflammatory cytokines. NF- κ B signalling requires IKK subunits which regulate pathway activation through I κ B phosphorylation. NF- κ B signalling is regulated through phosphorylation of p100 by the IKK α subunit of the IKK complex, which results in ubiquitination and subsequent partial degradation of p100 by the proteasome, releasing transcriptionally active p50/RelB complexes.

2.4.1.2 MAPK pathway

MAPKs are a family of serine/threonine protein kinases that direct cellular responses to a variety of stimuli, including osmotic stress, mitogens, heat shock, and inflammatory cytokines (such as IL-1, TNF- α , and IL-6), which regulate cell proliferation, differentiation, cell survival and apoptosis (Pearson *et al.*, 2001; Kaminska *et al.*, 2005). The mammalian MAPKs include extracellular-signal-regulated kinase ERK1/2, p38 MAP Kinase, and c-Jun N-terminal kinases (JNK) (Kim EK *et al.*, 2010). Each MAPK signalling pathway comprises at least three components: a MAPK, a MAPK kinase (MAPKK), and a MAPK kinase kinase (MAPKKK). MAPKKKs phosphorylate and activate MAPKKs, which in turn phosphorylate and activate MAPKs (Dhillon *et al.*, 2007). ERKs are generally activated by mitogens and differentiation signals, while inflammatory stimuli and stress activate JNK and p38 (Sabio *et al.*, 2014). MKK1 and MKK2 activate ERK1/2, MKK4 and MKK7 activate JNK, and MKK3 and MKK6 activate p38. Activation of the MAPKs, including Erk1/2, JNK, leads to phosphorylation and activation

of p38 transcription factors present in the cytoplasm or nucleus, which initiates the inflammatory response (Pearson *et al.*, 2001). This pathway mediates intracellular signalling initiated by extracellular stimuli, such as stress and cytokines. MAPKKKs phosphorylate and activate MAPKKs, which in turn phosphorylate and activate MAPKs. The mammalian MAPK family includes Erk1/2, JNK, and p38. In the Erk1/2 pathway, Erk1/2 is activated by MKK1/2, which is activated by Raf. In the JNK pathway, JNK is activated by MKK4/7, which is activated by MEKK1/4, ASK1, and MLK3. In the p38 pathway, p38 is activated by MKK3/6, which is activated by MLK3, TAK, and DLK. Activated MAPKs phosphorylate various proteins, including transcription factors, resulting in regulation of inflammatory responses. They are finely regulated by several mechanisms, including scaffolding of their components, and phosphorylation/dephosphorylation and compartmentalization of MAPKs.

2.4.1.3 JAK-STAT pathway

The highly conserved JAK-STAT pathway involves diverse cytokines, growth factors, interferons, and related molecules, such as leptin and growth hormone, and is a signaling mechanism through which extracellular factors can control gene expression (O'Shea JJ *et al.*, 2015). Receptor-associated JAKs are activated by ligands and phosphorylate one other, creating docking sites for STATs, which are latent, cytoplasmic transcription factors. Cytoplasmic STATs recruited to these sites undergo phosphorylation and subsequent dimerization before translocation to the nucleus (Walker *et al.*, 2005). Tyrosine phosphorylation is essential for STAT dimerization and DNA binding (Ivashkiv *et al.*, 2003). Therefore, JAK/STAT signalling allows for the direct translation of an extracellular signal into a transcriptional response. For example, binding of IL-6 family members to plasma membrane receptors activates the JAK-STAT proteins. STAT proteins translocated into the nucleus bind target gene promoter regions to

regulate transcription of inflammatory genes. Following IL-6 binding, signal is transduced by a receptor to activate the JAKs, which then activate STATs. STATs are dephosphorylated in the nucleus, leading to activation of downstream cytokines. JAK activation occurs upon ligand-mediated receptor multimerization because two JAKs are brought into close proximity, allowing trans-phosphorylation. The activated JAKs subsequently phosphorylate additional targets, including both the receptors and the major substrates, STATs. The JAK–STAT pathway is regulated at many steps by various proteins, including suppressor of cytokine signalling (SOCS) proteins, protein inhibitor of activated STAT (PIAS) proteins and protein tyrosine phosphatases.

2.5 Tlr (toll- like) receptor in relation with inflammation

Toll-like receptors (TLRs) are a family of proteins that are involved in the initial phase of host defence against invading pathogens. TLRs act as primary sensors of microbial products and activate signalling pathways that lead to the induction of immune and inflammatory genes (Takeda *et al.*, 2003) TLRs belong to a broader family of proteins, which include receptors for the pro-inflammatory cytokines interleukin (IL)-1 and IL-18. All members of this superfamily signal inflammation in a similar manner. This is due to the presence of a conserved protein sequence in the cytosolic domain called the Toll–IL-1 receptor (TIR) domain, which activates common signalling pathways, most notably those leading to the activation of the transcription factor NF- κ B (nuclear factor κ B) and stress-activated protein kinases (Imler *et al.*, 2001). Most investigations on TLRs have focused on cells of the innate system. Furthermore, most research on the biological implications of TLRs has centred on infections. This is because the patterns recognised by TLRs are principally from pathogens.

2.5.1 Transcription factors of inflammation

Signal transducers and activators of transcription (STATs), interferon regulatory factors (IRFs) and nuclear factor kB (NFkB) are major players among SRTFs. Different family members function in the establishment as well as the resolution or prevention of inflammation. This dual mode of macrophage activity during inflammation is represented by the polarization of macrophages into the proinflammatory M1 type and the inflammation-resolving M2 type.

Overview of STAT's, IRF's and NFkB transcription factors

2.5.1.1 STAT's

STATs form a family of 7 members (STATs 1-4, STATs 5a and 5b, STAT6). All family members function predominantly in the context of cytokine-responsive, two-component JAK-STAT pathways. When cytokine receptors bind their cognate ligands, one or more receptor-associated Janus protein tyrosine kinases (JAKs) are activated and phosphorylate latent STATs on a single tyrosine residue. In some STATs this leads to a reorientation of preformed dimers into a parallel arrangement (Mertens *et al.*, 2006) whereas others may dimerize de-novo. Dimerization is stabilized by reciprocal phosphotyrosine (pY) interactions with SH2 domains which are, among transcription factors, a distinguishing feature of STATs. Py-mediated dimerization exposes an unconventional nuclear localization signal that shifts the subcellular localization of STATs to the nucleus (Liu *et al.*, 2006). Homo-or heterodimeric STATs recognize a DNA sequence called gamma interferon- activated sequence (GAS, TTCN3-4GAA (Decker *et al.*, 1997). In contrast, STATs able to form a complex with a non-STAT subunit, IRF9, bind to a distinct sequence, the interferon-stimulated response element (ISRE). The ISRE is a hallmark of all type I and type III IFN-responsive genes (ISG) and a large fraction of IFNg-inducible genes. Both type I IFN (IFN-I: IFNa, IFNb, others) and type III IFN (IFN-III: IFNl) cause tyrosine

phosphorylation of STAT1 and STAT2, the resulting heterodimer forms an ISRE-dependent complex with IRF9 called ISGF3.

2.5.1.2 IRFs

The original description and eponymous function of IRFs derives from their activity as regulators of the genes encoding type I IFN (Miyamoto *et al.*, 1988). The minimal IRF binding site of the IFN β promoter, characterized by 5'-GAAA-3' motifs (Goodbourn *et al.*, 1988) is part of many ISRE sequences (5'-PuPuAAANNGAAAPyPy-3'). Not surprisingly therefore, a second identification of IRFs resulted from the purification of ISRE-associated proteins (Pine *et al.*, 1990). Subsequent work revealed a total of 9 family members in mice and men (IRF1-9). Common structural features of IRFs include an N-terminal DNA binding domain with 5 characteristically spaced tryptophanes and one of two structurally distinct C-terminal IRF association domains. In IRF9, but not other IRFs, the IAD contains a binding site for STAT2. The regulation of IRF transcriptional activity requires for some IRFs (IRF3, IRF5, and IRF7) the phosphorylation of serine residues within the IAD and C-terminus for dimerization and activation. For others (IRF1, IRF2, IRF4, IRF8), sporadic reports of phosphorylation events exist, but this modification is most likely not generally necessary to regulate transcriptional activity. IRF9 is unique as it has no known transcriptional activity on its own and is so far characterized exclusively as a subunit of ISGF3 or other complexes containing either STAT1 or STAT2.

2.5.1.3 NF κ B

Various canonical and non-canonical NF κ B complexes are formed by members of the Rel family of transcription factors which contain a Rel homology domain (RHD) for DNA binding and, in case of the RelA, RelB, and c-Rel family members, a C-terminal transactivation domain (Hayden

et al., 2012). The p52 and p50 proteins are formed from larger precursor protein (p100 and p105, respectively) by proteolytic processing. The major player among proinflammatory NFκBs, and the only one discussed here, is the heterodimer of RelA/p65 and p50. Its nuclear activity is restricted by inhibitors of NFκB (IκB, mainly IκBa) through a direct interaction that masks the nuclear localization signal. Activation of the IκB kinase complex (IKK complex, consisting of IKKα, IKKβ, and IKKγ/NEMO) causes the phosphorylation of IκBa on two critical serines which leads to its ubiquitination and subsequent degradation. In the innate immune system activation of the IKK complex is caused by all PRR, and by TNF receptor- as well as CD40-related receptor families. In the adaptive immune system NFκB is activated by these same receptor families and also by lymphocyte antigen receptors.

2.6 How natural products have helped in regulating pathways

The diversity of plant natural product (PNP) molecular structures is reflected in the variety of bio- chemical and genetic pathways that lead to their formation and accumulation. Plant secondary metabolites are important commodities, and include fragrances, colorants, and medicines. Increasing the extractable amount of PNPs through plant breeding, or more recently by means of metabolic engineering, is a priority. The prerequisite for any attempt at metabolic engineering is a detailed knowledge of the underlying biosynthetic and regulatory pathways in plants. Over the past few decades, an enormous body of information about the biochemistry and genetics of biosynthetic pathways involved in PNP production has been generated.

Plants produce a plethora of secondary metabolites, diverse both in structure and their biosynthetic origins. For any attempt at targeted metabolic engineering of plant natural product (PNP) biosynthesis, it is of utmost importance to understand the biogenesis of PNPs from

ubiquitous primary metabolites. The vast majority of PNPs can be categorized into three large classes: isoprenoids, phenylpropanoids, and alkaloids.

2.7 Bioactive peptides

Peptides are short chains of amino acids linked by peptide bonds. Chains of fewer than twenty amino acids are called oligopeptides, and include dipeptides, tripeptides, and tetrapeptides. Peptides are short, typically comprising 2–50 amino acids. Amino acids are also the building blocks of proteins, but proteins contain more. Peptides may be easier for the body to absorb than proteins because they are smaller and more broken down than proteins.

2.7.1 Biological activities of peptides that have been found

Bioactive peptides are the most common. Bioactive peptides are generally 3–20 amino acid residues in length and, although both animal and plant proteins are known to contain potential bioactive sequences, most studies to date have involved milk proteins. They are active once released by enzymatic hydrolysis by peptidases during food processing and/or during gastrointestinal digestion. In order to exert a positive health effect, bioactive peptides must cross the gastrointestinal (GI) barrier and survive enzyme degradation.

The following are the activities found over the years;

2.7.1.1 ACE Inhibitory Activity Peptides

These peptides are inhibitors of the angiotensin-1 converting enzyme (ACE or ACE-1) and can thus prevent hypertension. ACE has a relevant role in the regulation of blood pressure in the renin-angiotensin system because this enzyme converts the inactive decapeptide angiotensin I into the potent vasoconstricting octapeptide angiotensin II and this result in an increase in blood pressure. Such enzyme is also able to inactivate bradykinin. So, ACE inhibitory peptides can

reduce the blood pressure a few hours after oral administration through the inhibition of ACE that is a dipeptidyl carboxypeptidase usually membrane-bound in vascular endothelial cells.

2.7.1.2 Opioid Peptides

Opioid peptides have a good affinity for an opioid receptor and are thus able to exert opiate-like effects by affecting the nerve system and gastrointestinal functions. Peptides from exogenous sources are denominated exorphins. The stability and lower side effects are the main advantages of food derived opioid peptides when compared to endogenous and synthetic opioid peptides. Such peptides are usually characterized by a tyrosine residue at the amino terminal end and an aromatic residue located in the third or fourth position. Exorphins have been reported in hydrolyzates from milk casein, wheat gluten and blood haemoglobin.

2.7.1.3 Immunomodulating Peptides

Peptides exerting its action on immune system affect both the immune system and cell proliferation responses and have good applications in clinical medicine. So, immunomodulatory peptides can regulate lymphocytes proliferation in humans, modulate certain cytokines production, as well as stimulate the macrophages activity. Most of the reported immunomodulatory peptides are released from milk proteins either by enzymatic hydrolysis or by gastrointestinal digestion after consumption even though they may be scarce in the last case for any significant effects on human body. Enzymatic hydrolysis is necessary in order to get therapeutic amounts of immunomodulatory peptides. For instance, some milk caseins hydrolyzates stimulate the immune system while other peptides generated by pancreatin or trypsin may inhibit the proliferative responses of murine splenic lymphocytes and Peyer's patch cells.

2.7.1.4 Antimicrobial Peptides

Antimicrobial peptides have been mainly isolated from milk and egg and constitute a natural defense of the organism against pathogens. Antimicrobial peptides are effective against different bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* among others, as well as against yeast. The mode of action depends on the type of peptide but its effects are by forming pores on bacterial membranes, causing thinner membranes interacting with other components in the cell or acting in a detergent-like manner. The most studied is the fragment 17–41 of lactoferrin, known as lactoferricin. Other proteins that are good sources of antimicrobial peptides are ovotransferrin, lysozyme, alpha-lactalbumin and beta-lactoglobulin.

2.7.1.5 Antioxidant Peptides

Depending on the chemical reactions involved, antioxidant activity of peptides can be classified into two groups:

Those peptides able to reduce free radicals by hydrogen donation in a competitive reaction, and those peptides able to transfer one electron to reduce an oxidant. The methods used in the first case are oxygen radical absorbance capacity assay (ORAC), total radical trapping antioxidant parameter (TRAP) and b-carotene bleaching assay, while in the second case are 2,20-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzthiazoline- 6-sulfonic acid (ABTS) radical scavenging assay, ferric-reducing antioxidant power, and 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging activity. Antioxidant peptides may contribute to decrease the risk of cardiovascular disease as well as certain types of cancer. Such peptides prevent the formation of free radicals or introduce substances that compete for the existing radicals. Most of them have, between 4 and 16 amino acids, and the molecular mass ranges from 400 to 2000 Da. Radical-scavenging properties have been reported in peptides containing tyrosine, tryptophan and phenylalanine. If aromatic amino

acids are present in peptides at the water–lipid interface, such peptides can get access to scavenge free radicals from the lipid phase.

There are a lot of activities reported but these are few mentioned above.

Some sources of peptides include; Meat, Fish and shellfish, Beans and lentils, Soy, Oats, Flaxseed, Hemp seeds, Wheat etc

2.8 *Spinacea oleracea* L.

Spinach (*Spinacea oleracea* L.), an annual plant, is a green, leafy vegetable that can be grown in both spring and autumn. The nutritional value of fresh spinach, with 91% of moisture content, shows between 0.4% and 0.6% lipid content, around 2.9% protein content, and contains good levels of essential amino acids, except sulphurous amino acids (methionine) and tryptophan. Although the carbohydrate content is very low (2%–10%), the fibre content is high (2.2%). There are numerous health benefits associated with the consumption of spinach and these are attributed to its lipid-lowering properties and cardiovascular protection, antiobesity effects, hypoglycaemic activity, anti-inflammatory effects, anticancer properties, neuronal protection, anti-macular degeneration, among others. Fresh spinach is attributed antioxidant properties because it contains a large amount of phenolic or flavonoid compounds, chlorophylls, ferulic acid and caffeic acid, quercetin, patuletin, spinacetin, and jaceidin, which are mainly found in the leaves, with maximum levels in the summer. Spinach is native to central Asia, most probably Persia (Iran). Spinach (*Spinacea oleracea* L.) belongs to the family Chenopodiaceae. Spinach is annual for leaf production and biennial for seed production. It produces rosettes of fleshy leaves, which may be crinkled or smooth in the vegetative phase; later, the stem elongates and forms

flower stalks during the reproductive phase, with narrow, pointed leaves. The main objectives of spinach improvement are high yield, good quality of green leaf, uniformity, and resistance to major diseases. Breeding methods applicable to the improvement of cross-fertilizing vegetable crops may also be applicable to spinach improvement. Population improvement methods such as recurrent selection, mass selection, and progeny testing are suitable for the development of new variation.

Figure 1: Spinach (*Spinacea oleracea* L.)

CHAPTER THREE

Methodology

3.1 Ab Initio Database screening and modelling of the peptides

The database screening of peptides with anti-inflammatory properties were conducted using APD3 database (<http://aps.unmc.edu/AP/main.php>) (Wang *et al.*, 2016). The selections were based on the reported biological activities a presented in the APD3 database. The 3D structures of the selected peptides were obtained from the Protein Data Bank (<https://www.rcsb.org/>) (if available). Otherwise, the 3D structures of the peptides will be predicted by submitting their respective FASTA amino acid sequence into I-TASSER (<https://zhanglab.ccmb.med.umich.edu/ITASSER/>), an automated modelling server (Yang *et al.*, 2015; Zhang *et al.*, 2017). The best model for each peptide were selected based on the C-scores and further validated using the Structure Analysis and Verification server SAVES v5.0 (<https://servicesn.mbi.ucla.edu/SAVES/>) (Pontius *et al.*, 1996).

3.2 Physicochemical characterization

The physicochemical characterization of the respective peptides were predicted using ProtParam Tool on the SIB ExPASy webserver ProtParam tool (<https://www.expasy.org/tools/>) using mammalian as the defined organism (Artimo *et al.*, 2012). The computed parameters include the molecular weight, theoretical pI, estimated half-life, instability index, aliphatic index, and grand average of hydropathicity.

3.3 Molecular docking

The crystal structures of EGFR kinase, human HER2 Kinase (erbB2), and human mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase 1 (MEK1) were retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (<https://www.rcsb.org/>) with PDB IDs 4I23, 3PP0, and 3W8Q respectively. The structural bioinformatics studies of the selected peptides with the enzymes were computed using the HawkDock server (<http://cadd.zju.edu.cn/hawkdock/>) integrated with the ATTRACT docking algorithm, the HawkRank scoring function and the Molecular Mechanics/Generalized Born Surface Area (MM/GBSA) free energy decomposition analysis (Feng *et al.*, 2017; Weng *et al.*, 2019) and the interactions were visualized using PyMOL ver. 1.1eval (De Lano Scientific LLC, CA, USA).

3.4 Molecular Dynamics (MD) Simulations

The molecular dynamics simulations were carried out using the CABS-flex 2.0 server to evaluate the structural flexibility and stability within a nanosecond time scale of the ACE2-peptide complexes (Kuriata *et al.*, 2018). The root-mean-square fluctuations and contact maps were obtained.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULTS

4.1 Ab Initio Database screening and modelling of the peptides

The database used in this study is APD3 database (<http://aps.unmc.edu/AP/main.php>). Four peptides from spinach were retrieved from the database with the APD ID (APD00289, AP00290, AP00291, and AP00292) and with 25, 23, 24 and 38 amino acid residues respectively. The FASTA amino acid sequences of the peptides are presented in Table 1 with the assigned names. The stereo chemical quality of the predicted models and accuracy of the protein model was evaluated after the refinement process using Ramachadran Map calculations computed with the PROCHECK program. The result revealed that the modelled structure for SOP 1, SOP 2 , SOP 3 and SOP 4 has 45.5%, 42.1%, 45.0%, 29.0 % residue respectively in allowed region.

Table 1: Identification of the selected peptides from spinach and respective sequences considered for the study.

Assigned Name	APD ID	FASTA Sequence	Number of amino acids
SOP 1	AP00289	GIFSSRKCKTVSKTFRGICTRNANC	25
SOP 2	AP00290	MFSSKKCKTVSKTFRGPCVRNA	23
SOP 3	AP00291	MFSSKKCKTVSKTFRGPCVRNAN	24
		GIFSSRKCKTPSKTFKGYCTRDSNCDTSCRYEGYPAG	
SOP 4	AP00292	D	38

Figure 2: Ramachradan's maps of peptides obtained from APD3 database

4.2 Physicochemical characterization

Table 2 shows the physicochemical properties of plant-based peptides, which includes the molecular weights, theoretical isoelectric points, instability indexes, aliphatic indexes, and grand average hydropathy of each of the selected peptides predicted through ExPASy webserver ProtParam tool (<https://www.expasy.org/tools/>) in which mammalian was the defined organism. The results indicated that SOP 4 had the highest molecular weight and instability index while SOP 1 has the highest aliphatic index. The computational study also revealed that SOP2 and SOP3 had the highest isoelectric point. It was also observed that SOP2 has the highest grand average of hydropathicity as compared to other selected peptides.

Table 2: Physicochemical characteristics of the selected peptides

Peptide	Number of Amino acids	Molecular weight (Da)	theoretical isoelectric point	Estimated half-life (h)	Instability index (II)	Aliphatic index	Grand average of hydrophaticity (GRAVY)
SOP 1	25	2778.26	10.34	30	36.58	46.8	-0.376
SOP 2	23	2623.15	10.48	30	18.42	29.57	-0.365
SOP 3	24	2737.25	10.48	30	18.07	28.33	-0.496
SOP 4	38	4230.69	8.83	30	42.23	12.89	-1.058

4.3 Molecular Docking

The outcome of the molecular docking is presented in Table 3. The results reveal the energy scores for different models. The first model of each computation with the most negative energy score was selected as the score for each interaction. SOP 4 had the highest affinity with all the selected proteins, as indicated by the least value of each binding energy and assessment by MM/GBSA free energy computation through an approximation of solvent electrostatic contribution in the Poisson–Boltzmann model. The molecular interactions of peptides with the selected peptides of *Spinacea oleracea* are shown in Figure 3, while the interacting residues of the protein and peptide interface are also presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Binding score of docked complexes by MM/GBSA/Interactions between the ligands and peptides.

		EGFR kinase	erbB2	MEK1
SOP1	Binding Energy	-5.3	-11.18	-29.39
	Receptor interacting residues	ASP-166, ILE-167, THR-170, TYR-172	SER 55, SER-87, LEU-474, ARG-475, 515	ARG-111, SER-114, GLN-277, VAL-281, GLN-283
	Peptide interacting residues	SER-12, THR-14, PHE-15, ASN-24, CYS-25	MET-1, THR-14, ALA-23	VAL-11, PHE-15, CYS-8, 9, THR-10, VAL-11, SER-12
SOP2	Binding Energy	-9.68	-35.01	-23.12
	Receptor interacting residues	GLY-17, ASP-22, ILE-540	ARG-21, ILE-465, ILE-540	GLU -125, GLY-164, PHE-237, SER-267, GLU-303
	Peptide interacting residues	TYR-18, THR-20, ASN-24	CYS-19, ARG-21,	PHE-3, SER-4, THR-10, LYS-13, THR-14
SOP3	Binding Energy	-6.5	-34.24	-42.43
	Receptor interacting residues	LYS-119, ILE-123, 310, THR-314,	ALA-120, TRP-	GLN-18, LEU-54, ASN-318
	Peptide interacting residues	SER-12, PRO-18, CYS-19, ASN-22, ALA-23	GLY-1, ILE-2, PHE-3, SER-4, LYS-7	VAL-47, PHE-307, ARG-274, PRO-276, GLN-277, TYR-279, MET-293
SOP4	Binding Energy	-8.5	-33.15	-47.16
	Receptor interacting residues	GLY-111, ILE-282, GLU-286	GLN-150, GLY-284,	ASN-127, ASP-131, HIS-194
	Peptide interacting residue	MET-1, CYS-8, PHE-15, ASN-22, ALA-23	SER-12, THR-14, ALA-23	TYR-128, LEU-163, LYS-13, ARG-16, LYS-16, GLY-17, THR-20, ASP-26 ARG-30

Figure 3: 3D illustration of the interactions between the complexes of (A) EGFR kinase (B) erb2, and (C) MEK 1 with (i) SOP1 (ii) SOP2 (iii) SOP43 (iv) SOP 4: peptides from *Spinacea Oleracea*

4.4 Molecular dynamics simulations

The ligand-peptide interactions are further evaluated via molecular dynamics simulations analysis to examine the fluctuation of the individual amino acids in the complex and their conformational stability. The first model of each was chosen based on its best structural heterogeneity and stability. Significant changes were noticed in the structural flexibility of all the selected proteins based on The investigations of interactions of the selected compounds with the ligand based on molecular dynamics are presented in Figures 4, 5 and 6 respectively. The fluctuation plots showed that the fluctuation of the amino acids were high for the plots with bound ligands compared to the wild-type.

(i)

(ii)

(iii)

(iv)

(v)

Figure 4: Molecular dynamics of (i) wild type of human HER2 Kinase and its interaction with (ii) SOP1, (iii) SOP2, (iv) SOP3, and (v) SOP4

Figure 5: Molecular dynamics of (i) wild type of human mitogen-activated protein kinase 1 and its interaction with (ii) SOP1 (iii) SOP2, (iv) SOP3 and (v) SOP4

(i)

(ii)

(iii)

(iv)

(v)

Figure 6: Molecular dynamics of (i) wild type of EGFR kinase and its interaction with (ii) SOP1, (iii) SOP2, (iv) SOP3, and (v)SOP4

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 DISCUSSION

This present study employed computational study, as a predictive approach in the exploring anti-inflammatory peptides. The bioactive peptides in Spinach could be considered as functional products with substantial health benefits beyond basic nutrients. The diversity of bioactive compounds in spinach with new action of mechanisms has attracted the attention of scientists to use them as potential options of treatment against inflammation (Elkhateeb *et al.*, 2018). The distribution of the main chain bond lengths and bond angles were found to be within the limits for these proteins. In the Ramachandran plot analysis, the residues were classified according to its regions in the quadrangle. The red regions in the graph indicate the most allowed regions whereas the yellow regions represent allowed regions. Glycine is represented by triangles and other residues are represented by squares. Such figures assigned by Ramachandran plot represent a good quality of the predicted models.

The calculated isoelectric point (pI) will be useful because at pI, solubility is least and mobility in an electro-focusing system is zero. Isoelectric point (pI) is the pH at which the surface of protein is covered with charge but net charge of protein is zero. At pI proteins are stable and compact. The computed isoelectric point (pI) will be useful for developing buffer system for purification by isoelectric focusing method. The computed pI value shows that all the proteins are greater than 7 ($pI > 7$) which reveals that these proteins are basic in nature. The instability index provides an estimate of the stability of protein in a test tube. There are certain dipeptides, the occurrence of which is significantly different in the unstable proteins compared with those in the stable ones. This method assigns a weight value of instability. Using these weight values it is

possible to compute an instability index (II). “A protein whose instability index is smaller than 40 is predicted as stable, a value above 40 predicts that the protein may be unstable” (Guruprasad *et al.*, 1990). The instability index values for the spinach anti-inflammatory proteins were found to be ranging from 18.07 to 42.23. The result shows that the peptides can be considered stable. The aliphatic index (AI) which is defined as the relative volume of a protein occupied by aliphatic side chains (Alanine, Valine, Isoleucine and Leucine) is regarded as a positive factor for the increase of thermal stability of globular proteins. Aliphatic index for the anti-inflammatory protein sequences ranged from 12.89 to 46.8. The low aliphatic index of these anti-inflammatory protein sequences indicates that these proteins may be unstable for a wide temperature range as they may contain low amount of hydrophobic amino acids.

The Grand Average hydropathy (GRAVY) value for a peptide or protein is calculated as the sum of hydropathy values of all the amino acids, divided by the number of residues in the sequence. GRAVY indices of the proteins are ranging from -0.365 to -1.058. This low range of value indicates the possibility of better interaction with water.

The interactions between the selected peptides and the proteins were assessed through molecular docking analysis. This study predicted the putative molecular mechanism of action of these compounds through computational analyses. The first model of each molecular interaction was selected as the best docked complex based on the c-scores (Chapados *et al.*, 2004). Binding energy is released when a drug molecule associates with a target, leading to a lowering of the overall energy of the complex. So the more negative the free binding energy, the more stable the interacting complex. All the peptides showed relative high affinity towards the selected targets, most especially SOP 4. SOP 4 showed a relatively high affinity toward all the selected proteins, most especially R3 represented by human mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase 1 (MEK1).

The docking studies showed that the peptides could have reasonable biological effect that could interfere with the target proteins and limit the activities of EGFR kinase, human HER2 Kinase (erbB2), and human mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase 1 (MEK1).

The flexibility of the peptides and its complexes with the selected proteins were simulated using an online tool (CABS-flex 2.0 server). The peptides-ligands interactions generated fluctuation maps which were later evaluated based on the RMSF (root-mean square fluctuation). A wild and bound type simulation was conducted; wild (the selected enzymes only) and bound (the peptides with the enzymes).

For the first enzyme, it was observed that the binding of the peptides to the enzyme (bound-type) could inhibit the expression of that particular enzyme and thereby, induce anti-inflammatory properties. This was observed based on the flexibility of the fluctuation plots while comparing the wild to bound-type. Same result was observed for the other two enzymes; therefore we can say that all the selected peptides could repress or inhibit the expression of the enzymes which can induce anti-inflammatory properties. The changes in the fluctuations of the residues at the pockets where the peptides binding occurred indicate the interactions of the selected peptides at the active sites of the ligands could enhance the rigidity of the amino acids in the active sites. Thus, the binding of the peptides with the ligands could influence the ligands interactions and subsequent biologic functions and the innate capability to initiate cellular responses. This could corroborate the therapeutic actions of these compounds to disorders that are associated with inflammatory responses (Oso *et al.*, 2017)

5.2 Conclusion

This study has shown that bioactive peptides from Spinach (*Spinacea oleracea*) could be developed and explored for their use in peptide-based drugs against inflammatory disorders through their effects on the selected peptides in this study.

5.3` Recommendation

Further experimental studies are therefore recommended to validate the theoretical potential of the selected peptides.

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